

HyDelta 4

WP2e – Effects of high-speed hydrogen gas velocity, including future 16 bar(g) networks

D2e.1 – Hydrogen gas velocity in 16 bar grids

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Document summary

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Tag (Choose only ONE):

Technology and Safety

- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education

Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

In this study, the risks of high-speed operation in future hydrogen networks were addressed. In particular for the future 16 bar(g) networks, the potential harmful effects were considered, not only in a relative manner (benchmark to previous operation with natural gas) but also in an absolute manner.

The pulsation, vibration and noise effects for hydrogen at increased flow velocity are comparable to operation with natural gas. However, while the source strength does not increase, an upward shift in frequency is observed. Field testing even indicates that vibration and radiated noise effects are more favourable with hydrogen. For hydrogen, the risks on flow-induced effects are considered manageable with existing industrial design codes and practices, up to flow speeds of 50 m/s. Beyond this limit, detailed analysis for flow-induced pulsation effects is recommended, to endorse the design. For intrusive equipment (e.g. thermowells), selection and design of hardware 'fit-for-service' in high-speed conditions remains mandatory.

Erosion can be a limiting factor for hydrogen transport, particularly when (continuous) high flow velocities are combined with high solid particle concentrations. However, overly conservative assumptions for flow velocity profiles and unrealistically high solid contents shall be avoided. In the present study, more realistic scenarios were developed, indicating upper limits for flow speed, for various realistic values of solid particle concentration. As a general remark, increased flow velocities can be accepted, provided that the hydrogen stream has minimal solid particle fouling. This shall be ensured by clear production and storage processes and adequate filtering. In particular, if solid particle concentrations do not exceed 1 mg/kg, an upper design limit for 50 m/s flow velocity is considered appropriate for 16 barg hydrogen networks.

Managementsamenvatting

In deze studie zijn de risico's van hogesnelheidsbedrijf in toekomstige waterstofnetwerken onderzocht. Met name voor de toekomstige 16 bar(g)-netwerken zijn de potentiële schadelijke effecten niet alleen relatief (benchmark ten opzichte van operatie met aardgas) maar ook absoluut beschouwd.

De pulsatie-, trillings- en geluidseffecten van waterstof bij verhoogde stroomsnelheid zijn vergelijkbaar met die van aardgas. Hoewel de bronsterkte niet toeneemt, wordt een verschuiving naar hogere frequenties waargenomen. Veldmetingen tonen aan dat de trillings- en geluidseffecten bij waterstof zelfs gunstiger zijn. Voor waterstof worden de risico's van door de stroming veroorzaakte effecten als beheersbaar beschouwd met de bestaande industriële ontwerpnormen en -praktijken, tot stroomsnelheden van 50 m/s. Boven deze limiet wordt een gedetailleerde analyse van stromings-geïnduceerde pulsatie-effecten aanbevolen voor een acceptabel ontwerp. Voor ingestoken apparatuur (bijv. thermowells) blijft de selectie en het ontwerp van hardware die geschikt is voor gebruik bij hoge snelheden van essentieel belang.

Erosie kan een beperkende factor zijn voor waterstoftransport, met name wanneer (continu) hoge stroomsnelheden worden gecombineerd met hoge concentraties vaste deeltjes. Overdreven conservatieve aannames voor stroomsnelheidsprofielen en onrealistisch hoge concentraties vaste deeltjes moeten echter worden vermeden. In deze studie zijn realistischere scenario's ontwikkeld, die bovengrenzen voor de stroomsnelheid aangeven, voor verschillende realistische waarden van de concentratie vaste deeltjes. In het algemeen kunnen hogere stroomsnelheden worden geaccepteerd, mits de waterstofstroom minimale vervuiling door vaste deeltjes vertoont. Dit moet worden gewaarborgd door schone productie- en opslagprocessen en adequate filtering. Specifiek wordt een bovengrens van 50 m/s voor de stroomsnelheid bij 16 barg waterstofnetwerken als passend beschouwd, indien de concentratie vaste deeltjes niet hoger is dan 1 mg/kg.

Summary

Following the initial investigations in HyDelta1, the risks of high-speed operation in future hydrogen networks were addressed in more detail. In particular for the future 16 bar(g) networks, the potential harmful effects were considered, not only in a relative manner (benchmark to previous operation with natural gas) but also in an absolute manner. The mechanisms of system pressure loss, flow-induced turbulence, flow-induced pulsations, control valve noise and radiated external noise were investigated. The effects for hydrogen at increased flow velocity are comparable to operation with natural gas, with an upward shift in source frequencies. Field testing indicates that vibration and radiated noise effects are more favourable with hydrogen, compared to natural gas. For hydrogen, the risks on flow-induced effects are considered manageable with existing industrial design codes and practices, up to flow speeds of 50 m/s. Beyond this limit, detailed analysis for flow-induced pulsation effects is recommended. For intrusive equipment (e.g. thermowells), selection and design of hardware 'fit-for-service' in high-speed conditions remains mandatory, for the gas speed limits as indicated in HyDelta1.

Erosion can be a limiting factor for hydrogen transport, particularly when high flow velocities coincide with elevated solid particle concentrations. However, results of this study show that erosion risks derived from conservative worst-case assumptions (as used in HyDelta1, including continuous operation at maximum flow velocity combined with unrealistically high solid contents) can be significantly overestimated.

When more representative and realistic assumptions are applied for both flow profiles and solid particle concentrations, the allowable flow velocities increase substantially. In practice, gas networks exhibit strongly time dependent flow behavior, with operation at or near maximum capacity occurring only for limited periods. Applying measured load duration curves instead of constant flow assumptions leads to a major reduction in the predicted cumulative erosion.

In addition, the currently applied maximum solid particle limit of $100 \text{ mg}/(\text{n})\text{m}^3$, originating from natural gas regulations, does not reflect realistic steady-state operating conditions and leads to physically implausible erosion predictions when applied continuously. The use of targets based on significantly lower solid concentrations is therefore recommended. These lower solid concentrations are confirmed from more recent design guidelines, as well as measurements in (natural) field cases. Also, the typical production processes for hydrogen are expected to result in a clean influx into the distribution network. The study illustrates the sensitivity by applying solid concentrations of 1, 10 and 100 mg/kg.

Based on these findings, it is concluded that for limiting the effect of erosion for hydrogen transport it is required to:

- Maintain a clean pipeline system through adequate filtration and control of solid contamination sources.
- Limit maximum flow velocities, while understanding the annual flow distribution can support the design for higher allowable flow velocities.
- Provide additional erosion allowance by selecting an increased wall thickness at potentially critical locations such as elbows and tee-sections.

The use of larger bend radii and the avoidance of unfavorable geometries as elbows and tee-sections could theoretically help, but are in practice constrained by existing network layouts and design standards.

In conclusion, the analysis demonstrates that, under realistic assumptions and with appropriate system design, hydrogen transport at higher flow velocities is technically feasible without erosion becoming a limiting factor. Still, to achieve very high flow velocities, low levels of solid particles shall be ensured by clean hydrogen production, adequate filter design and periodic filter inspection. In particular, if solid particle concentrations do not exceed 1 mg/kg, an upper design limit for 50 m/s flow velocity is considered appropriate for 16 barg hydrogen networks

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1. Introduction

1.1 Energy transition and hydrogen value chain

Hydrogen is expected to play a key role in the Dutch energy strategy to decarbonize industries and to provide balance to the renewable energy supply. Besides the national hydrogen transmission infrastructure from HyNetwork Services (HNS), hydrogen distribution grids will need to be developed to connect the HNS backbone with regional supply and demand, and to interconnect local supply and demand.

The Netherlands has an extensive pipeline infrastructure for the transport and storage of natural gas. For reasons of personal and environmental safety and to ensure reliable supply, the infrastructure is built according to standards and norms for pipeline integrity. Currently, the reliability is ensured by complying with design codes and by using systematic approaches for maintenance and troubleshooting.

1.2 Re-use of existing pipelines and design of new pipelines

As The Netherlands have an extensive infrastructure for natural gas distribution, future application of hydrogen will involve re-purposing of existing networks. In other areas, however, also application of newly built networks will be used. A specific example is the application of distribution networks, to be operated at 16 barg. This is a new operating pressure, that was not previously used for natural gas distribution grids. The impact of such 16 barg network, is the focus of HyDelta4, Work Package 2.

Thus, two distinct perspectives on the future hydrogen supply infrastructure are identified:

1. re-use of existing (natural gas) infrastructure for hydrogen
2. new infrastructure for hydrogen

For the first category, the existing infrastructure is to be re-purposed as much as possible, with obvious benefits for capital expenditure. In such cases, a common simplified approach is to assume that in the future hydrogen economy, the **same energy transport capacity** is required, as was the case for natural gas. An example was the project HyDelta1, work package 1E [1], where exactly this presumption was made. Considering the typical thermodynamic properties of hydrogen and natural gas, this implies that hydrogen shall be transported at a significantly higher transport velocity (x3). For example, a typical maximum flow velocity for sizing of new natural gas networks was 20 m/s (determined by the grid operator). Then, for hydrogen, this would imply a maximum flow velocity of 60 m/s, which is a very high value. This increased transport velocity will have consequences for the risk on flow-induced phenomena, such as pulsations, vibrations and noise. The basic premise of this re-use benchmark is that in the natural gas infrastructures, no issues are observed. Thus, if the flow-induced effects for high-speed hydrogen remain comparable (or more benign) than in the case of natural gas, the risks are considered acceptable. It shall be noted that the presumption, though useful and informative, may and will be an over-simplification. It is very likely that in the future hydrogen operation in existing infrastructure, the production and consumption profiles will be significantly different. This will be particularly true for the regional networks, where local producers and different consumers may be sharing the existing infrastructure. Hence, it is good to extend the *relative* benchmark (“... effects not getting worse in hydrogen, compared to natural gas ...”) with a more *absolute* assessment of risk on flow-induced effects, for each specific network. Methods and references for such absolute assessments are included in this study report.

For the second category (new networks), the relative benchmark is not (necessarily) a requirement. Here, the line sizes can be newly designed, depending on the forecast of production and consumption. With conventional flow speed limits (e.g. 20 m/s), an appropriate line size may be chosen. Still, to limit the line diameter as much as possible, and to avoid over-conservative design (large pipe diameters), it is extremely valuable to understand the mechanisms and risks for high-speed flow in networks. Then, more dedicated targets for flow speed can be used, to achieve the optimal balance between lean diameter sizing and quantified risks.

1.3 Research questions

In this work package WP2e, the main research questions are:

- What is the impact of the new operational conditions of hydrogen at 16 bar(g), with respect to flow-induced phenomena?
- Are new flow-induced issues to be expected, that are not prone to occur in the conventional 8 bar(g) distribution networks?
- Are the existing design codes, with respect to flow-induced phenomena adequate to ensure a safe and reliable design of 16 bar(g) networks?
- If concerns may exist, what are necessary steps to effectively mitigate these? For example by additional research, testing, standardization etcetera?

The main risk identified in HyDelta1, was erosion of pipe lines under high-speed flow conditions, in combination with corrosive particles (sand and dust) in the flow [1]. The risk was identified on various parts of the system where high flow speeds may occur, in combination with fouling the flow: in the high-pressure part (TSO's scope) as well as low-pressure parts (DSO's scope). Several industrial standards and guidelines are available to predict the effects of erosion. These standards find their origin in the upstream oil and gas production industry, and not from the practice of gas distribution. The modelling basis for HyDelta1 was taken from the DNV Recommended Practice O501 [2].

The conclusions from HyDelta1 were that in case of the worst-case combination of maximum flow speed (60 m/s for Hydrogen) and maximum fouling (maximum legal allowable content), unacceptable erosion rates of piping are expected. However, also in case of the traditional benchmark case for natural gas (20 m/s at maximum fouling), unacceptable erosion rates are predicted. This latter observation is not in accordance with user experiences in the Dutch natural gas distribution grid. In HyDelta1, it was concluded that the prediction models in the standards are fit-for-purpose, but that the worst-case scenario considered (maximum speed, maximum fouling, on a continuous basis) is far too conservative. Hence, the additional research questions for HyDelta4, WP2e are:

- Can the operating scenario be formulated in a more realistic manner, for the prediction of erosion?
- Can the production profiles (flow speed as function of time) from historic gas distribution be used, for update prediction of erosion rates?
- Are quantitative user experiences available with respect to actual fouling in the gas flow? For permanent operation, and in incidental cases (e.g. installation and maintenance)?
- To which extent are these historic user experiences with natural gas distribution applicable for future distribution of hydrogen?
- Can an upper limit for the maximum allowable operating velocity be quantified?
- Can start-up scenarios be proposed (after installation or maintenance), that minimize the risk on erosion due to entrained solids?

In case the design of a system has not considered the effects of high flowspeed adequately, one of the harmful consequences could be excessive flow-induced vibrations. In case of such excessive vibrations, the presence of hydrogen may enhance the effects of fatigue. This can be due to the degradation of the steel material structure due to hydrogen entrapment (embrittlement) and/or due to acceleration of crack growth. These effects are not part of this study, but are extensively treated in other references (e.g. HyDelta4, WP2C). This present report aims at providing guidance to judge the risks and methods to achieve acceptable vibrations, thereby eliminating the risks on fatigue.

1.4 Project plan

The project plan is based on the HyDelta4 agreement [3], in particular the description of WP2e “prognosis for high-speed H₂ gas velocity, including future 16 bar(g) networks”. By means of literature survey and high-level modelling, the questions above are addressed. The intermediate results have been communicated and discussed during periodic technical update meetings with TNO and the Expert Assessment Group (EAG). The final results are included in this report.

2 High flow speed effects in 16 bar(g) networks

2.2 Previous works and conclusions (HyDelta1)

In HyDelta 1, the harmful effects of flow-induced phenomena were studied in detail. The re-purpose benchmark was used as the basic premise of the study.

- It was assumed that the traditional natural gas infrastructure has no (excessive) issues with flow-induced phenomena, designed for and operated at a maximum flow velocity of 20 m/s.
- For the future operation with hydrogen, the same mechanisms were studied, at an increased flow velocity of 60 m/s.
- After comparing the relative effects between these two cases, the future risks on issues due to flow-induced phenomena were judged. Design standards and mitigation techniques were discussed as well.

The general conclusion of this work was that for future hydrogen distribution at the assumed increased flow velocity, the majority of the flow-induced phenomena will have comparable risk profiles as the classical natural gas distribution. The main exception is the phenomenon of erosion. The phenomenon of erosion will be handled in more detail in chapter 3.

A basic summary of the mechanisms, with a ranking of the risk priority is shown below (1=high risk, 3=low risk):

Priority	Mechanism	Conclusion (benchmark H ₂ to natural gas)
1	Erosion	As a result of high flow velocities, erosion potential is dramatically increased.
2	Flow-induced noise	In-line pulsation levels will be higher, with a tendency to higher frequency. However, the transfer through the pipe wall will be more favourable. Net effect to be studied on a case-by-case basis.
2	Flow-induced pulsations	Similar or smaller pulsation amplitude, with a tendency to higher frequency. In particular relevant for high-pressure and large-diameter parts of the distribution network.
2	FIV Intrusive equipment	Traditional designs (long, straight) are at risk, if operated beyond 28 m/s. For high flow speed, re-purposed equipment shall be considered.
3	Pressure loss over the pipe lines	Similar pressure loss.
3	Flow-induced turbulence	Effects are similar or more benign. Existing pipe design and supporting is adequate to arrest effects of turbulence.
3	Acoustics-induced vibration	In-line pulsation levels will be higher, with a tendency to higher frequency. However, the coupling to the pipe wall will be less effective, due to the large impedance mismatch between fluid and pipe wall, and the large speed-of-sound in the case of hydrogen.

2.3 Field tests on 8 bar(g) district station

For the important mechanisms of flow-induced pulsation, vibration and noise, the results in HyDelta1 were not fully conclusive. While the in-line noise levels in case of hydrogen appear more intense, the coupling to the pipe wall (vibration) and the radiation from the pipe wall are less effective. A generic assessment of the net effect appeared difficult, due to the large variety and the limited accuracy of the prediction models.

As a practical verification, the measurement data acquired by TNO during a trial (executed by KIWA for Netbeheer Nederland) in 2020 is presented below. During the trial, a similar benchmark was performed as during the numerical assessment in [1]. A gas district station was operated under two test conditions: with natural gas and with hydrogen. The setup is illustrated in Figure 2-1; the outlet line size is 4". The pressure conditions were comparable for the two tests: 8 bar(g) inlet pressure and 100 mbar(g) outlet pressure. Each test consisted of a sweep of the flow capacity from minimum to maximum and back. The maximum flow velocity for the two test series was ~20 m/s and ~60 m/s, for natural gas and hydrogen respectively (Figure 2-2). The tests included measurement of pulsations (in-line noise), vibrations and radiated external noise (at a distance of 0.1 and 1 meter from the control valve). More detailed information on the test setup and conditions can be found in [4].

Figure 2-1. Trial setup: gas district station, including inlet valve, dust filter, pressure regulator and outlet valve.

Figure 2-2. Flow sweep during the tests: gas velocity downstream the control valve, for natural gas (blue) and hydrogen (green).

The results for the internal pressure pulsations are significantly affected by acoustic resonance effects in the measurement tubes. This makes a direct comparison of natural gas and hydrogen difficult.

The results for the vibrations downstream of the control valve are illustrated in Figure 2-3. With increasing flow capacity, the amplitude increases. Hereby the vibration amplitude for natural gas is higher than the pulsation amplitude for hydrogen.

For the radiated noise, the overall comparison is **more favourable** for hydrogen. This can be seen in Figure 2-4. The maximum noise level (inside the cabinet) is 87 dB(A) for natural gas and 82 dB(A) for hydrogen. The expected frequency shift is observed (x3), see Figure 2-5 .

For this specific test case (considered representative for 8 bar(g) network district stations), the theoretically predicted increase in in-line pulsations for hydrogen could not be observed. The net effect (combination of the in-line source and the transfer through the pipe wall) on the vibrations and on the radiated noise is more favourable in case of hydrogen, by at least a factor 2 and with a margin of typically 5 dB(A), respectively.

Figure 2-3. Accelerations, all 3 directions, on the piping for the flow sweeps for natural gas (blue) and hydrogen (green). Measured on flange downstream the control valve (A4).

Figure 2-4. Noise radiation for the flow sweeps for natural gas (blue) and hydrogen (green). Noise levels measured at 0.1m from the control valve (N1).

Figure 2-5. Noise spectrum for natural gas (blue) and hydrogen (green), at maximum capacity.

2.4 Evaluation for 16 bar(g) networks

In this section, the specific aspects for the 16 bar(g) networks were investigated, in a similar manner as the investigation in HyDelta1 [1], for the typical circumstances in the future 16 bar(g) networks (operational conditions, piping layouts). Strictly speaking, however, the relative benchmark does not apply for this case, as there is no historic experience with 16 bar(g) natural gas networks in The Netherlands. For that reason, also more absolute assessments has been undertaken – where possible - for the flow-induced phenomena, using industrial guidelines for design of process installations.

For the 16 bar(g) networks, the analysis was based on the assumption of steel pipes. Even though alternative non-metallic pipe materials may be available (at lower weight and potentially lower cost), there is a consensus to use steel pipes [5]. The main reasons are the experience and the commercial availability and security in supply chain. More information can be found in other tasks in the HyDelta4 Work Package 2. The 16 bar(g) networks have been studied, for line sizes up to DN400, which is considered a representative choice for the upper limit of the line size.

Though the design standards and consumer profiles of hydrogen distribution networks are still a topic in full development, some specific cases were shared by partners in the Expert Assessment Group. The line diameters of these systems were sized in a cautious manner with respect to the maximum hydrogen flow velocity. The maximum hydrogen flow speed remain below 25 m/s, at the outlet of the receiving gas station. Still, in the present study, the potential harmful effects will be studied over a much larger range, up to the maximum of 60 m/s, as used in HyDelta1.

2.4.1 Piping pressure loss

Fluid flow in pipelines of distribution networks will be typically fully turbulent. This is true for both natural gas and hydrogen, over the full range of realistic transport scenarios. Even a ‘low-turbulent scenario’ of a flow speed of 1 m/s in a DN50 pipeline would have a Reynolds number $\sim 1e4$, which is above the laminar-turbulent transition point.

In turbulent pipe flows, the turbulent energy is often expressed in terms of kinetic energy ρU^2 : fluid density multiplied with the flow speed squared. Many physical phenomena are dictated by this quantity. For example, the pressure loss per unit length in a pipeline is described in terms of ρU^2 , multiplied by a friction factor that depends on pipe line diameter, the wall roughness and on Reynolds number. As outlined in [1], the kinetic energy for natural gas at 20 m/s and hydrogen at 60 m/s is roughly comparable. The difference in {flow speed}² is practically compensated by the difference in density:

$$\rho_{NG} U_{NG}^2 \approx \rho_{H2} U_{H2}^2$$

Thus, also the pressure loss for the natural gas and hydrogen, is very comparable. No issues are expected with piping pressure loss in future 16 bar(g) networks, even at elevated flow velocities.

2.4.2 Flow-Induced Turbulence

The turbulent structures in the flow interact with the pipe wall. In case the turbulence intensity is very high, the loading of the structure due to the flow may lead to significant vibration. This potentially

harmful phenomenon is often referred to in industrial standards as Flow-Induced Turbulence (FIT). The frequency spectrum of this ‘internal noise’ source is typically broadband (stochastic) with most energy contained at the lower frequencies (<100 Hz). Especially in case the piping layout is very flexible and/or poorly damped severe vibrations may be observed in high-speed flow. Unfavourable mechanical layout of piping (leading to increased risk of pipe vibration) includes:

- Piping with very long pipe support spans → low mechanical rigidity
- Non-buried (above-ground) piping → low mechanical damping

Piping with closely spaced supports, or buried piping are generally exposed to lower risk on vibration.

For process pipe systems, the risks can be assessed by using the Energy Institute guidelines for the Avoidance of Vibration-Induced Fatigue Failure (AVIFF) [6].

In [1], the **relative comparison** of hydrogen versus natural gas was done. It was demonstrated that the risk on flow-induced turbulence is comparable to risk for natural gas, for the various parts in the hydrogen transport network. However, for the hydrogen conditions of 16 bar(g), there is not a reference base-line of “trouble-free operation at 16 bar(g) with natural gas up to 20 m/s”. Hence, the relative comparison with historic experience fails. Therefore, it was investigated if also the **absolute assessment** of the future hydrogen conditions in a 16 bar(g) network highlights risks of concern. For this purpose, the AVIFF guidelines were used.

The first screening in AVIFF is on the absolute value of the kinetic energy. The risk classification is shown below:

Table 2-1. Initial (qualitative) assessment on risk on Flow-Induced Turbulence [6].

Item	Aspect	Applicable process fluid(s)	Likelihood Classification		
			Low	Medium	High
1	What is the maximum value of kinetic energy (ρv^2) of the process fluid within the system under consideration?	All	$\rho v^2 < 5,000 \text{ kg/m s}^2$	between $5,000 \leq \rho v^2 < 20,000 \text{ kg/m s}^2$	$\rho v^2 \geq 20,000 \text{ kg/m s}^2$

Turbulence ρU^2 levels below 5000 kg/ms^2 are considered low-risk, turbulence levels in the (broad) range between $5000\text{-}20000 \text{ kg/ms}^2$ pose a medium risk, while values $> 20000 \text{ kg/ms}^2$ are considered high-risk. An overview is given in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2. Typical values for turbulent kinetic energy, for natural gas and hydrogen distribution network parts.

Natural gas @ 8 bar(g)			
U [m/s]	ρU^2 [kg/ms ²]		
10	710		
15	1599		
20	2842		
25	4440		
Hydrogen @ 8 bar(g)		Hydrogen @ 16 bar(g)	
U [m/s]	ρU^2 [kg/ms ²]	U [m/s]	ρU^2 [kg/ms ²]
10	79	10	149
20	317	20	595
30	713	30	1340
40	1267	40	2382
50	1980	50	3721
60	2851	60	5359
Natural gas @ 40 bar(g)			
U [m/s]	ρU^2 [kg/ms ²]		
10	3444		
15	7750		
20	13777		
25	21527		

Figure 2-6. Typical values for turbulent kinetic energy, for natural gas and hydrogen distribution network parts.

The first impression for the 16 bar(g) hydrogen network flow conditions is that the turbulent energy is much less severe than the natural gas conditions at 40 bar(g). However, the turbulent energy is higher

than for natural gas at 8 bar(s). Still, the absolute values of ρU^2 are “low risk” up to speeds of 57 m/s. At 60 m/s, the risk is marginally “medium”.

A closer inspection, using the more elaborate quantitative assessment in [6], also considers the effects of the mechanical layout of the pipe system. Even though these mechanical properties differ from case to case, in general it can be stated that for buried pipe systems, the stiffness classification can be conservatively assumed “medium-stiff” (lowest mechanical natural frequency $\sim 7\text{Hz}$). Then, for line sizes from DN50 to DN400, acceptable risk scores are obtained (low LOF), see Table 2-3.

Based on the above considerations, the risk on fatigue failures on lines in 16 bar(g) hydrogen networks operated up to 60 m/s is considered very low.

Table 2-3. Quantitative assessment, for various line sizes, 16 bar(g) Hydrogen flow.

Line size	U [m/s]	ρU^2 [kg/ms ²]	Risk	Stiffness classification (schedule STD)	LoF ¹	Advised support span ²
DN50	60	$5.4 \cdot 10^3$	Medium	Medium-Stiff	0.03	<4.8m
DN100	60	$5.4 \cdot 10^3$	Medium	Medium-Stiff	0.03	<6.1m
DN200	60	$5.4 \cdot 10^3$	Medium	Medium-Stiff	0.03	<8.3m
DN400	60	$5.4 \cdot 10^3$	Medium	Medium-Stiff	0.03	<11.7m

¹ LOF=Likelihood-of-Failure, a quantitative risk score, for fatigue failure due to FIT. A value < 0.29 is considered acceptable.

² Maximum allowable pipe support spans, to ensure the “Medium-stiff” classification. Only applicable for un-buried piping.

2.4.3 Flow-Induced Pulsations

Another mechanism that can be harmful in case of high-speed flow configurations are pulsations generated at closed side branches. A closed side branch is any dead-leg in the system that is exposed to a grazing flow in the main line (Figure 2-7). This may be a ‘permanent’ dead-leg or a ‘temporary’ dead-leg, for example in case of district station maintenance. This phenomenon is normally labelled as Flow-Induced Pulsation (FIP). In the previous work the mechanism is described in detail [1]. The physical phenomenon is a feedback mechanism between flow instability at a branch connection (vortex shedding) and acoustic resonance inside the branch ($\frac{1}{4}\lambda$ wavelength). Though various configurations may be susceptible for flow-induced pulsation, the most common and critical type is the grazing flow of a straight mainline along a closed branch (FIP type A), see Figure 2-7.

Figure 2-7. Flow-induced pulsation effect: grazing flow along a closed side branch [6].

In case of a strong feedback, pressure pulsations may be generated within the branch, but also radiated toward the rest of the upstream and downstream pipe system. The pulsations are typically tonal and low-frequent ($<100\text{Hz}$). In general, the source frequency depends on the flow speed and the diameter of the header and the branch (Strouhal relation). The pulsation amplitude scales with ρU^2 .

For the same branch configuration, in hydrogen conditions, the resonance frequency of the branch will be 3 times higher than for natural gas (speed-of-sound in hydrogen is 3 times larger). To excite this high-frequency resonance, also flow speed of roughly a factor 3 is needed. This is exactly the benchmark assumption of the previous study. However, the source strength will be similar (or slightly lower) in amplitude, as this scales with primarily with ρU^2 . The overall conclusion is that the equally energetic phenomena can be expected for hydrogen, but at a frequency three times higher than with natural gas. In principle, the upward frequency shift is not favourable because restraining mechanical vibration at higher frequency requires a stiffer construction.

In [1], it was explained that the urgency of this type of FIP source is higher in the large-dimension, high-pressure system of the HTL network (most practical example of FIP problems are found in such systems with high capacity and large-diameter headers and branches). Still, for the future 16 bar(g) hydrogen networks, the screening for risks on FIP was executed in a similar way in the present study.

Also for FIP phenomena, the metric ρU^2 is the leading quantity to judge the risks. According to Table 2-1 and Table 2-2, the value is $<5000 \text{ kg/ms}^2$ for almost the entire range of gas velocities. Based on TNO's experience with several detailed FIP-analysis, system with "low-risk" values for ρU^2 can be considered safe without additional analysis.

The following general recommendations are proposed to assess and mitigate the risks for FIP, for 16 bar(g) hydrogen networks:

- Screen the risks according to the AVIFF guidelines. In case of system with a classification ρU^2 "medium" or "high", proceed with the quantitative assessment.
- In case of high Likelihood-of-Failure (LOF) the design shall be critically reviewed and, if needed, optimized:
 - Minimize local gas velocity, by local enlargement of the main line at T-branch connections to closed dead-legs.

- Optimize the fitting diameter of side branches
- Minimize the length of closed branches
- Ensure a robust mechanical layout of the branches and appended equipment.
- Limiting the flow velocity for hydrogen to a maximum of 50 m/s will reduce the risk classification to 'very low' and can be considered a safe limit.
- Perform a detailed Flow-Induced Pulsation analysis in systems with closed side branches, if the gas velocity exceeds 50 m/s. This requires a detailed numerical simulation model, including the piping layout and the location of the pulsation sources. A typical example of a model for such detailed analysis is given in Figure 2-8 (for this specific example, the flow velocity in the header (38 m/s) did not lead to any flow-induced pulsation issues in the system (<< the pulsation limits in industry standards)). Typical recommendations that follow from such detailed analysis are optimization of the diameter and length of closed side branches.

Figure 2-8. Example of a detailed simulation model, for calculation of Flow-Induced Pulsation effects. Flow measurement streets in a storage system.

2.4.4 AIV (acoustic-induced pulsations and vibrations)

Acoustics-Induced Vibration (AIV) concerns the failure mechanism by which a high-frequency broadband spectrum of noise rapidly leads pipework to fatigue failure. Typical sources of AIV in natural gas transmission systems are elements in which pressure is suddenly reduced: relief or blow-down valves, control valves and restriction orifices. The generated acoustic spectrum has a typical broadband character ('roaring' at lower frequency range, 'screaming' at the higher frequency range). The noise is characterized by its amplitude and by the peak frequency, see Figure 2-9. Noise generated by pressure let-down devices may lead to integrity issues. Incidents have been reported in literature but are relatively rare. Areas at increased risk are:

- Configurations with high in-line noise levels.

- Lines with large pipe diameter and small wall thickness.
- Configurations with welded discontinuities, such as small branch connection to a parent pipe, T-joints and welded pipe shoes. Circumferential welding, for example at elbows and flanges is not considered a critical discontinuity.

Figure 2-9. Typical frequency spectrum of noise due to pressure-reduction devices: broadband spectrum with a broad peak around the centre frequency (1.5 kHz, in this example).

In the previous investigation it was observed that the in-line noise in case of hydrogen may be higher than in case of natural gas. This observation followed from similarity analysis of the two gas conditions, again, for equal energy flow through the pressure reducing element. Two independent models were used: the semi-empirical prediction models from the AVIFF Guidelines [6] and the more elaborate model from the IEC-60534-8 standard [7]. The offset is not exactly the same in these two references, but an increase of 2-6 dB is observed in the produced sound power, for hydrogen. Also, an upward shift in the peak frequency is predicted by a factor ~ 3 , similar to previous noise mechanisms. Note that all predicted values for sound power level are for in-line noise levels. These are typically much larger than noise levels as experienced outside of the pipe, due to the 'shielding effect' of the pipe wall (transmission loss). The relation between internal and external noise levels will be discussed in more detail in section 2.4.5.

The most typical (continuous) sources of AIV associated with the 16 bar(g) hydrogen network are the pressure control valves, that reduce the pressure stepwise. These PCVs are found at the interface with the 40 bar(g) network (gas receiving stations) and at the interface with the 100 mbar(g) network (district stations). Both examples are considered below and compared with the corresponding PCV noise generation in case of an 8 bar(g) network, from the HyDelta1 analysis.

Gas receiving station

For the traditional 8 bar(g) networks the PCV reduces the pressure from typically 40 bar(g) to 8 bar(g). For the new 16 bar(g) networks, the pressure reduction is **smaller**: from 40 bar(g) to 16 bar(g). Assuming the same, typical reference capacity for natural gas of 42.000 Nm³/h, the acoustic source power is computed for a variation of inlet pressures. The results are illustrated in Figure 2-10. For the 8 bar(g) network, the source power for hydrogen is 5-6 dB higher than for natural gas. For the 16 bar(g) network, the same offset of 5-6 dB is observed. However, the **absolute** source level for the 16 bar(g)

hydrogen network is lower, by 3-11 dB, depending on the inlet pressure. Note that the 16 bar(g) prediction for natural gas, is a rather theoretical case: in The Netherlands ,no practical experiences are available for such system. Still, the PCV in receiving stations for 16 bar(g) hydrogen networks will be a less strong source than for the 8 bar(g). The risk on integrity or noise issues is considered low.

Figure 2-10. Source power levels for gas receiving station. Left: 8 bar(g) network, right: 16 bar(g) network.

Gas district station

For the traditional 8 bar(g) networks the PCV reduces the pressure from 8 bar(g) to 100 mbar(g). For the new 16 bar(g) networks, the pressure reduction is **larger**: from 16 bar(g) to 100 mbar(g). Assuming the same, typical reference capacity for natural gas of 4.000 Nm³/h, the acoustic source power is computed for a variation of inlet pressures. Again, in both configurations the relative offset between hydrogen and natural gas is 5-6 dB. The absolute source strength for hydrogen in 16 bar(g) networks is higher than in 8 bar(g) networks, due to the larger pressure drop over the PCV. However, as in both the networks the pressure ratio over the valve is large, the difference is not very large. At nominal pressure conditions, the source in 16 bar(g) networks is approximately 3 dB higher. With the (more positive) results from the field tests, as described in section 2.3 [4], it is expected that also in the 16 bar(g) networks, the AIV effects will not lead to severe issues.

Figure 2-11. Source power levels for gas district station. Left: 8 bar(g) network, right: 16 bar(g) network.

Also for the mechanism of AIV, instead of the *relative* benchmark, a more absolute metric for the risk is required. The formulations in AVIFF [6] and the NORSOK L-002 standard [8] are proposed to this purpose. Only the critical example of the district station (reducing the pressure from 16 bar(g) to 100 mbarg) is studied, at a typical reference capacity for natural gas of 4.000 Nm³/h. The absolute, quantitative screening in AVIFF happens in 2 steps:

1. Calculation of the source strength metric, with a formula including mass flow, pressure ratio and gas parameters. The calculated result is compared to an empirical threshold of 155 dB. If the source strength is lower, the risk is low.
2. If the source strength is higher than 155 dB, a follow-up calculation shall be done, returning a Likelihood-of-Failure (LOF). This calculation involves the source strength, the pipe wall thickness, the presence of welded discontinuities down the valve etc. If the LOF is <0.29 , the risk is judged acceptable.

The screening method is summarized in a sheet below, for the district station. For the LOF calculation, a welded discontinuity (for example a ½” weldolet connection) is assumed, closely placed downstream the control valve. Both the power level screening (< 155 dB) and the LOF evaluation are a “pass”, meaning that the risk on fatigue failure is very low. Also the alternative NORSOK L-002 screening (which is fairly similar to the AVIFF screening, except for an alternative acceptance criterion including the diameter/wall thickness ratio) returns a “pass”.

The main argument for the favourable screening results is the limited mass flow, due to the low density of hydrogen. For several industrial systems, similar screening methods were performed in the past years, confirming the generally favourable results for hydrogen pressure-reduction and blow-down systems.

Screening approach based on Energy Institute Guideline (AVIFF), technical module T2.7			
Input data			
Tag blow-down device		District Station	
Upstream Pressure	P1	17	[bar (a)]
Downstream Pressure	P2	1,1	[bar (a)]
Mass flow	W	1141	[kg/h]
Temperature	Te	283,15	[K]
Molecular Weight	Mw	2,22	[g/mol]
Specific heat ratio (CP/CV)	γ	1,41	[-]
Outer Diameter main line	Dext	168,3	[mm]
Wall thickness main line	T	7,11	[mm]
Outer Diameter side branch	dext	21,34	[mm]
Wall thickness side branch	t	3,73	[mm]
Distance between source and welded discontinuity	ldis	1	[m]
Required mass flow	Qreq	1141	[kg/h]
Low-noise trim, noise reduction	Δ PWL	0	[dB]
Output data - Sound Power Level screening			
Pressure ratio over the restriction/valve	R	15,45	[-]
Critical pressure ratio	Rcrit	1,90	[-]
SFF, correction factor for sonic flow	SSF	6	[dB]
Sound Power Level, C&M/ Eisinger	PWL	140,3	[dB]
Sound Power Level, AVIFF, incl SFF	PWL incl SFF	146,3	[dB]
Attenuation to welded discontinuity	Δ PWL	-0,4	[dB]
Sound Power Level, AVIFF, incl SFF, at welded discontinuity	PWL incl SFF	146	[dB]
Output data - LoF screening			
Ratio ext diameter / wall thickness		23,7	[-]
Ratio of main line/ SBC diameter	Dext / dext	7,89	[-]
	s	68,2	[-]
	a	0,940	[-]
	B	134,879	[-]
	log10(N)	17,477	[-]
	N	2,997E+17	[-]
	FLM1	0,686	[-]
	FLM2	0,200	[-]
	FLM3	1,000	[-]
	Lf	-1,88	[-]
	Lf, truncated	0,00	[-]
Likelihood-of-Failure at welded discontinuity	LoF	0,29	[-]

Figure 2-12. Example of a screening for Gas District station, hydrogen 16 bar(g) network (AVIFF screening [6]). The screening result is a “pass”.

Screening approach based on NORSOK L-002:2016, annex A			
Input data			
Tag blow-down device		District Station	
Upstream Pressure	P1	17	[bar (a)]
Downstream Pressure	P2	1,1	[bar (a)]
Mass flow	W	1141	[kg/h]
Temperature	Te	283,15	[K]
Molecular Weight	Mw	2,22	[g/mol]
Outer Diameter main line	Dext	168,3	[mm]
Wall thickness main line	T	7,11	[mm]
Are precautionary design measures taken (NORSOK A.5)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	FALSE	
Is the source a PSV?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	FALSE	
Distance between source and welded discontinuity	Ldis	1	[m]
Required mass flow	Qreq	1141	[kg/h]
Low-noise trim, noise reduction	ΔPWL	0	[dB]
Output data - Sound Power Level at welded discontinuity			
Sound Power Level, C&M / Eisinger	PWL	140,3	[dB]
Attenuation to welded discontinuity	ΔPWL	-0,4	[dB]
Sound Power Level, NORSOK	PWL	140	[dB]
Output data - Acceptance criterion			
Ratio inner diameter / wall thickness	Di / T	21,7	[-]
Acceptance level (A.5)	PWL _A	170,9	[dB]
Extra allowance due to precautionary design measures		0,0	[dB]
Extra allowance for PSV		0,0	[dB]
Total acceptance level		170,9	[dB]

Figure 2-13. Example of a screening for Gas District station, hydrogen 16 bar(g) network (NORSOK L-002 screening [8]). The screening result is a “pass”.

2.4.5 Radiated noise

The conclusions of the previous section on Acoustic-Induced Vibration indicate that the risks on fatigue failure in hydrogen pressure-letdown systems are generally low. A final aspect, that is related to AIV, is the radiated noise from the piping. The noise is generated inside the piping (the in-line pulsation caused by the control valve is the primary source) and transferred via the pipe wall to the environment. The transfer through and the radiation from the pipe wall is a complex phenomenon. Quantitative modelling depends on the line size, the pipe wall thickness and the pipe wall material. Also the impedance mismatch between the fluid inside the pipe, the pipe wall and the fluid outside the pipe (air) is relevant. All these effects are frequency-dependent, as is the spectrum of the in-line source. Empirical prediction models for these mechanisms can be found in VDI 3733 standard [9] and in the IEC-50634-9 standard [7].

In section 2.3 it was demonstrated that the radiated noise of a system with a control valve (gas district station) is lower for hydrogen, compared to the same layout with natural gas. This specific case (8 bar(g)) may be representative also for a larger range of conditions. The same physical mechanisms will be found at 16 bar(g), and it is very plausible that the same trends are observed for the 16 bar(g) conditions.

To better understand the mechanisms, as a first step, the interference diagrams are presented for natural gas and hydrogen. In such diagrams, the coupling efficiency between the internal acoustic modes and structural pipe wall modes are illustrated. The acoustic modes are observed at frequencies that are dictated by the inner diameter and the speed-of-sound. The structural modes are dictated by the pipe diameter and wall thickness and material properties of the pipe wall. Several acoustic and structural modes are illustrated in Figure 2-14 and Figure 2-15, respectively.

Figure 2-14. Acoustic modes in a uniform pipe: plane wave (top left) and higher-order modes, along circumferential and radial node lines.

Figure 2-15. Structural circumferential modes ($i=0$ is 'breathing' mode, $i=1$ is 'bending' mode).

In the interference diagram, the acoustic modes inside the pipe (blue dots) are compared with the structural modes of the pipes (red dots). Note that for these diagrams analytical models are used, assuming a simplified layout of a straight, uniform pipe. For a typical example (DN300, pipe class 19CS01) the interference diagrams for natural gas and hydrogen are shown in Figure 2-16. The modes are clustered around the 'nodal diameter orders'. The reason is that efficient coupling of acoustic and mechanical modes only occurs if the mode shape is similar. For example, acoustic modes with 2 circumferential nodes ($m=2$) couple efficiently with structural modes with the same number of circumferential nodes ($i=2$). In Figure 2-16, the structural modes are the same for both gas conditions as the pipe layout is assumed the same. However, the acoustic modes are very different. For natural gas, several acoustic modes are present in the frequency range of interest, where also structural modes exist. The difference is explained by the speed-of-sound: for natural gas the speed-of-sound is in the order of 400 m/s, while for hydrogen, the speed-of-sound is typically 1250 m/s. The consequence is that for natural gas, there are several 'coincidences' between acoustic and structural modes and the pipe wall can be efficiently triggered by the in-line pressure fluctuations (in this example between 2500 and 4500 Hz). For hydrogen, however, there is no such coincidence and the in-line pressure

fluctuations will not trigger the pipe wall efficiently. This is another contributing factor to the fact that AIV is less severe generally for hydrogen, than for natural gas.

Figure 2-16. Interference diagram for DN300 steel pipe. Left: natural gas; right: hydrogen.

Finally, several industry standards present empirical model for the break-out noise, describing the noise attenuation of the pipe wall. As an illustration of the main effects, the formulation in the VDI 3733 standard is used [9]. The noise reduction of the pipe R_R (the attenuation of internal sound power to external radiated sound power) contains several contributing terms:

$$R_R = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{c_{pipe} \rho_{pipe} t}{c_{gas} \rho_{gas} D_i} \right] + A(f) + C$$

The first term involves the wall thickness t and inner diameter D_i and the impedance mismatch (ρc) between process gas and pipe wall material. The impedance mismatch for hydrogen is always larger than for natural gas, due to the low density. Hence, the noise break-out due to this effect will be **lower** for hydrogen than for natural gas.

The second term $A(f)$ is frequency-dependent and depends on the pipe wall properties (density, speed-of-sound, diameter, wall thickness). $A(f)$ is minimal in the frequency range where maximum coincidence occurs between acoustic and structural modes (the minimum is called the ‘ring-frequency’). For very low frequencies, $A(f)$ is high and the pipe wall provides a high noise reduction. For very high frequencies, $A(f)$ is also high and the pipe wall provides a high noise reduction. For intermediate frequencies around the ring frequency, the noise reduction is relatively small, see Figure 2-17. Thus, the net effect does depend on the frequency shape of the source as well as on the pipe wall layout. Hence, it is difficult to make a generic statement if this effect will be favourable for hydrogen compared to natural gas. It may be favourable or unfavourable. However, given the relatively broad frequency bandwidth of the source, the effect is expect to be weak or neutral.

The third term C is a constant factor, depending on the overall piping layout (presence of flanged elements and elbows).

Figure 2-17 presents the effects for the term $A(f)$. The example is for various configurations that are expected as typical for 16 bar(g) networks: DN200, DN250, and DN300 steel piping. The horizontal coloured bars indicate the typical frequency range of the in-line noise source (control valve from previous examples). For natural gas 1-15 kHz, and for hydrogen and upward frequency range 3-45 kHz. This figure illustrates that it is very difficult to make a generic statement on favourable or unfavourable noise radiation for hydrogen. The frequency band of maximum in-line noise and the frequency band of minimum pipe wall transmission loss may overlap more-or-less, depending on the line size and

operational conditions. The practical tests described in section 2.3 are considered a fair representation of the actual behaviour in practical (8 bar(g)) circumstances. Similar conclusions are expected for the 16 bar(g) case.

Figure 2-17. Typical curves for noise reduction, factor $A(f)$. Minimum noise reduction around 5-8 kHz. The coloured lines indicate the frequency range of the in-line noise sources, for natural gas and hydrogen.

2.4.6 Intrusive equipment

In process installations, on key locations process instrumentation will be installed to control the process. For example in mixing stations, measuring and control stations and gas receiving station. The most familiar example of intrusive equipment is the thermowell, but also Wobbe (gas composition) meters and V-cone type flow meters are intrusive objects in the flow.

An important design evaluation is the screening of the risk of flow-induced vibration on these devices. The intruded object will be exposed to the flow, and flow instability (vortex shedding). The downstream (von Karman) vortex street in the wake of the object will cause a fluctuating force. The frequency of this force depends (linearly) on the flow speed, see Figure 2-18. If the frequency of the flow instability couples with a mechanical resonance frequency of the intruded object, large vibrations and cyclic stresses may be observed, with fatigue failure as ultimate consequence. Screening methods for such object can be found in mature industry standards, such as ASME PTC 19.3 TW-2016 [10]. See [1] for more detailed description.

Figure 2-18. Thermowell dynamic forces & vibration directions.

For newly designed systems, such as in the 16 bar(g) hydrogen networks, these intrusive elements are to be designed 'fit-for-service', using existing industrial design standards. In [1], a maximum flow velocity for re-use of existing equipment for future hydrogen services was specified as follows:

- Maximum 28 m/s for regional networks (design pressure 20 bar(g))
- Maximum 38 m/s for national networks (design pressure 80 bar(g))

In specific design studies, a more detailed analysis was done, using Finite Element Modelling of the thermowell. Such detailed analysis may eliminate part of the conservatism. In a specific case (flow metering station, 80 bar) a robust, but standard, thermowell design was endorsed up to flow speeds of 50-60 m/s.

It is recommended to use the industry standard screening methods, for all newly designed thermowells. In case the flow-speed is too high and cannot be reduced, either a more detailed (less conservative) analysis shall be done, or a special design shall be chosen. An example of such a special design is shown in Figure 2-19, where the helical rake shape has as purpose to disturb the flow instability and hence limit the excitation of the device.

Figure 2-19. Example of helical design thermowell (www.mac-weld.com).

Special equipment (e.g. control valves, non-return valves, static mixers) shall be endorsed by the manufacturers, according to regular industry standards.

2.5 Conclusions

The evaluations from the previous work [1] on risks of high-speed flow with hydrogen can be generalized to a large extent to the 16 bar(g) hydrogen conditions. There are no paramount changes in gas thermodynamic properties, physical phenomena or system layout that jeopardize the previous conclusions.

However, contrary to e.g. the 8 bar(g) and 40 bar(g) networks, there is no extensive user experience with 16 bar(g) networks with natural gas. Hence, the relative benchmark philosophy of the previous study had to be partly abandoned. To complement the relative assessment and to enable to draw conclusive statements, the screening for the flow-induced mechanisms in 16 bar(g) networks was executed in a more absolute sense. This was done, using industrial design guidelines, such as AVIFF, IEC-60534-8, Norsok L-002, VDI 3733 and ASME PTC 19.3.

Pipeline pressure loss and flow-induced turbulence (FIT) are expected to remain very similar to the natural gas experience. The pressure fluctuations are broadband in nature, with an emphasis on the lower frequencies. Screening of risks (and possible optimization of line size diameter and mechanical layout) in case of increased velocities ($U > 50$ m/s) is recommended [6].

The risks of flow-induced pulsations (FIP) at closed side branches will be comparable to the natural gas experience, with a upward frequency shift, in case of high hydrogen flow speeds. The pressure fluctuations are tonal in nature, with an emphasis on the lower frequencies. Screening of risks (and possible optimization of line size diameter and branch connection layout) in case of increased velocities is recommended [6]. For very high hydrogen flow velocities ($U > 50$ m/s), a detailed flow-induced pulsation analysis is recommended.

The in-line pressure fluctuations due to pressure letdown devices (AIV, acoustic-induced vibrations) may be more severe than with natural gas, with an upward frequency shift, according to industrial prediction standards. The pressure fluctuations are broadband in nature, with an emphasis on the higher frequencies. However, the coupling to the structural modes of the pipe wall will not be efficient in case of hydrogen. Hence, the risk screening of hydrogen cases does not highlight concerning risks, even for the most severe pressure let-down from 16 bar(g) to 100 mbar(g). In case of very large capacities required (> 12.000 Nm³/h), the pressure let-down may be best achieved with multiple parallel control valves, instead of a single large one, to minimize the risks. Options for low-noise design of control valves are available in industry, which may be mobilized upon need.

Increased radiated noise from piping in the vicinity of in-line noise sources is not considered a risk. Due to the large impedance mismatch of hydrogen with the pipe wall, the break-out noise will be limited. This is confirmed with field tests executed for 8 bar(g) conditions with natural gas and hydrogen. Similar results are expected for the 16 bar(g) conditions.

Intrusive equipment, such as thermowells, may be subject to integrity issues in case of high flow speeds. Here, the upward shift in excitation frequency (linear with flow speed) is the critical effect. Intrusive equipment shall be designed 'fit-for-service', which will limit the options for re-use in case of high-speed hydrogen. Screening with industrial design guidelines is recommended for new equipment [10]. In case of non-compliance with the design guidelines at very high speeds, more dedicated FEM analysis may be considered for less conservative assessment. Options for extra robust designs of thermowells are available in industry, which may be mobilized upon need.

3 Erosion modelling and assessment

As observed in HyDelta1, erosion may be a critical factor that impacts on the system integrity, if continuous operation will occur at very high flow velocity in combination with very high solid particle concentrations. In the additional analysis presented in this chapter, an attempt will be made, to quantify more realistic operating scenarios, compared to the absolute worst-case as presented in HyDelta1.

3.2 Guidelines and important parameters

Several industry standards and recommended practices are available for predicting erosion in pipelines. Most of these originate from the upstream oil & gas production domain rather than gas distribution practice. For HyDelta1, the modelling basis followed DNV Recommended Practice O501 for managing sand production and erosion [2].

The predicted loss of material E_m [kg/s] is taken as:

$$E_m = K U_p^n F(\alpha) m_p$$

Where K [m/s^{-n}] and n [-] are coefficients dependent on the pipe material, U_p [m/s] is the particle impact velocity and m_p [kg/s] is the solid mass flow rate that the flow is transporting. The function $F(\alpha)$ corresponds to a correction factor for the particle impact angle α and the ductility class of the material. The influence of the pipe geometry is incorporated through the $F(\alpha)$ term, as this factor reflects how impact angle distributions change with the geometry of the system. In HyDelta1 it was concluded that regardless of the geometry, the conclusion when comparing natural gas to hydrogen are similar and an elbow configuration was selected.

An operational gas network logically does not only consist of elbows, but also extensive lengths of straight piping, as well as reducers, tee sections, and other fittings. Among these components, elbows are generally recognized as the most critical locations with respect to erosion. Tee sections typically exhibit erosion rates comparable to, or lower than erosion rates observed in elbows, whereas reducers show lower erosion rates, with at least a factor two lower for very large diameter transitions and substantially lower for smaller diameter transitions. Erosion rates in straight pipe sections are typically an order of magnitude (or more) lower for identical operating conditions. Consequently, the present assessment focuses on erosion at elbows, which are considered representative of the worst-case scenario within the network. The elbows considered in this study report are the typical R=1.5D elbows. These are commonly used in industry. Only in exceptional cases (tight spaces), small curvature radii are used, notably R=1D. The impact was studied in the model and it was concluded that the difference of sharp bends (R=1D) with default design (R=1.5) is typically 5%: higher erosion rates in case of small-curvature elbows. If under exceptional circumstances, the system under consideration contains sharp elbows, it is advised to adopt an extra safety margin of 5% on the maximum allowable speeds presented in the annex of this report. Other configurations that have been considered in this study are illustrated in Figure 3-1. Generally, the formulation for maximum allowable flows speeds in elbows can be considered the most conservative and therefore also applicable to the other components.

Figure 3-1. Components considered for erosion analysis (straight pipe, reducer, default elbow, short-radius elbow and T-joint).

The particle impact velocity is the only parameter associated with the flow velocity. At high flow velocities the solid particles in the pipeline will be lifted and transported along with the gas, and therefore the particle impact velocity is equal to the gas flow velocity.

To enable a consistent comparison between natural gas and hydrogen the following assumptions have been taken in the previous investigation [1]:

- In the hydrogen re-use scenario, the same amount of energy is transported as with natural gas. This results in a flow velocity of hydrogen which is three times as large as for natural gas.
- Pipes are made of steel, HDPE and PVC. Numerical examples in the current report are for the 8bar and 16bar cases, using steel material.
- Erosive agent is sand, where a nominal particle diameter of 100 micrometers has been used.
- Maximum solid particle concentration used based on *Besluit kwaliteit leefomgeving* [11].
- Elbow radius is a standard 90-degree elbow geometry. Elbows with larger bend radii are generally expected to experience lower erosion rates, with erosion levels approaching those of straight pipe sections as the bend radius increases. However, since 90-degree elbows represent the normal applied configuration this is used as a representative assumption for the analysis.

A difficulty in establishing a generic benchmark is that the maximum solid rate stated by the on *Ministeriële Regeling Gaskwaliteit* is expressed as $100 \text{ mg}/(\text{n})\text{m}^3$. The composition of the gas leads to different fluid densities at normal conditions, meaning that the actual maximum solid particle rate differs when comparing different gas compositions. As there is no particular reason to expect that pipes with hydrogen will contain more solids than those with natural gas, HyDelta1 adopted a more pragmatic approach. In this approach, comparable solid mass flow rates were assumed for both gases, and therefore the normal density of natural gas was applied when converting the limit of $100 \text{ mg}/(\text{n})\text{m}^3$ to a mass based solid flow rate for both natural gas and hydrogen.

In

Table 3-1, a typical result following the same procedure and parameter set as in as in HyDelta-1 are summarized, for 8 barg and 16 barg steel DN200 lines with an indicative solids particle concentration corresponding to the $100 \text{ mg}/(\text{n})\text{m}^3$ specification for natural gas. Values are the predicted wall-thickness loss in mm per year for an steel elbow configuration.

Table 3-1. Predicted wall thickness loss due to erosion at various flow velocities, following same procedure as in HyDelta-1.

Line pressure	Gas	Flow velocity	Wall thickness loss
8 barg	Natural Gas	10 m/s	0.031 mm/year
8 barg	Natural Gas	20 m/s	0.37 mm/year
8 barg	Hydrogen	30 m/s	0.54 mm/year
8 barg	Hydrogen	60 m/s	6.5 mm/year
16 barg	Hydrogen	30 m/s	1.1 mm/year
16 barg	Hydrogen	60 m/s	13.7 mm/year

The following main observations are made:

- The predicted erosion rates are high, including the existing natural gas cases. For example, at a flow velocity of 20 m/s, a predicted erosion rate of 0.37 mm/year is not consistent with operational experience, which indicates no observable wall thickness degradation for natural gas systems.
- The predicted erosion rate for hydrogen is approximately 17 times higher than for natural gas. Which difference is primarily due to the higher flow velocity of hydrogen.
- Increasing the line pressure from 8 barg to 16 barg increases the predicted erosion rates by approximately a factor of two, assuming that the flow velocity remains unchanged.

While gas properties such as density and viscosity are fixed for a given operating condition (pressure and temperature), several additional parameters in the erosion correlation have a significant influence on the predicted erosion rates. Two of these parameters, particle velocity and solid particle concentration, were assumed to be constant in the HyDelta1 analysis. In the present analysis, these are examined in more detail in the following sections.

- Particle velocity, which influences the erosion rate exponentially. The exponent n typically ranges between 2 and 3, giving velocity a dominant influence on erosion predictions. However, the flow velocity is a design parameter where the maximum value can be estimated once the maximum capacity and process conditions are known.
- Solid particle mass flow, which influences erosion linearly. The solid particle concentration which determines the solid mass flow is difficult to estimate reliably. Historic operational data on solid contamination levels are very limited.

The effect of the solid particle size distribution is embedded in the function $F(\alpha)$. To make the impact of the particle size more visible the effect is shown in Figure 3-2 for a DN200 steel elbow with the maximum solid particle concentration. On the left the erosion is predicted for natural gas with a line pressure of 8 barg and a constant flow velocity of 20 m/s. On the right the erosion is predicted for hydrogen for line pressures of 8 barg and 16 barg for a constant flow velocity of 60 m/s.

Figure 3-2. Erosion prediction as function of the particle diameter for natural gas and hydrogen for a DN200 steel elbow configuration. Same parameters are used as in

Table 3-1 with the 20m/s flow velocity for natural gas and 60 m/s for hydrogen..

The curve increases linearly with particle diameter up to a threshold particle size of approximately 55 µm for natural gas and 16 µm for hydrogen. Beyond this threshold, a further increase in particle size no longer influence the predicted erosion rate. Because this threshold depends on the gas parameters, its value differs for natural gas and hydrogen. For the analysis in this report, a nominal particle size of 100 µm is used, consistent with the assumptions in HyDelta1. For the example shown, particle sizes larger than this threshold have no additional effect. Smaller particles below the threshold particle size, result in lower erosion rates. For hydrogen the threshold value is lower, meaning that hydrogen exhibits a faster increase in erosion rate for small particle sizes compared to natural gas. The nominal particle size of 100 µm is considered an adequate basis for the analysis.

3.3 Realistic scenarios: gas velocities

For the erosion assessment presented in section 3.2, a constant and continuous flow velocity was initially assumed. While this approach allows for a straightforward comparison between natural gas and hydrogen scenarios, it does not reflect the actual operating conditions of gas transport networks. In such networks, assuming a flat flow velocity at the maximum possible speed is very unrealistic. Instead, capacity profiles typically show a significant variation throughout the year. The shape of the flow distribution curves depends strongly on the type of consumers connected to the network.

To assess the impact of more realistic flow profiles on the predicted erosion rates, historical flow data from Dutch ‘Gas Ontvangst Stations’ (GOS, gas receiving station) have been analysed. This historic data concerns natural gas service, not hydrogen. In total, 22 datasets were collected, provided by members of the EAG. Of these, 21 datasets correspond to GOS stations supplying natural gas to regions with a mixed demand profile, consisting of both industrial customers and households. The remaining dataset represents a network supplying exclusively industrial consumers, without residential demand. This dataset was included to illustrate a limiting case of a (nearly) constant supply of hydrogen. All datasets originate from the year 2024, meaning that data profiles may differ in years with cooler periods with higher heating demand.

Figure 3-3 presents the load duration curves of all datasets over the year 2024. These curves show the number of hours of which a certain capacity level is exceeded, expressed as a fraction of the maximum measured capacity in that year (normalized). The results demonstrate substantial differences in usage patterns between regions. For several datasets, the load is zero for a significant portion of the year, with only a very short duration of the maximum load. This behaviour can be explained because (for example) biomethane injection was fully covering the demand, resulting in no net off-take at the corresponding GOS station during those periods. The curves cover a broad area of the map, where the ‘flattest curve’ (in this example the green line) will be most critical for the potential effects of erosion.

Figure 3-3. Load duration curves. Load as percentage of the annual maximum capacity for 22 Dutch GOS stations. The industrial-only region shows a more constant profile.

The dataset representing an exclusively industrial region shows a distinctly different behaviour. As expected, the load duration curve for this region exhibits a much more constant flow distribution across the year, reflecting the relatively steady demand profile typical of industrial consumers compared to residential heating demand. It has a long, sustained operation at a high percentage of the maximum capacity (note that in this industrial example, the line diameter sizing was such that the flow speeds at maximum capacity were not very high: $\ll 20$ m/s).

For each of the 22 datasets, the predicted annual erosion rate based on the measured, actual flow distribution was compared to the erosion rate obtained using a constant flow at the maximum level. The resulting ratio of these erosion predictions are shown in Figure 3-4.

For datasets 1 to 21 (mixed industrial and residential regions), a large variation in erosion ratios is observed, ranging from a factor of 19 up to 112. This indicates that assuming a constant flow distribution can lead to a substantial overestimation of erosion in regions with highly intermittent or seasonally dominated demand. In contrast, for dataset 22 (industrial-only region), the erosion prediction based on the realistic flow profile is reduced by approximately a factor of 3 compared to the constant-flow assumption, reflecting the more uniform operating conditions.

Figure 3-4. Reduction factor of erosion prediction when using realistic flow profiles (Figure 3-3) compared to constant flow distribution.

These results demonstrate that, depending on the expected demand profile of a region, a significantly more realistic erosion estimate can be obtained by applying an actual flow profile instead of a constant flow distribution. It is important to note that this analysis only quantifies the *relative* effect of using a realistic flow profile compared to a constant one. The *absolute* erosion rate remains strongly dependent on the maximum transport capacity of the region and the associated flow velocities, which ultimately govern the erosion mechanism.

3.4 Realistic scenarios: solid particle concentrations

The solid particle concentration parameter used in the initial assessment was based on the maximum allowable value specified in the *Ministeriële Regeling Gaskwaliteit* [11]. However, this value is not considered realistic as a constant operational value for several reasons.

First, the predicted erosion rates in

Table 3-1 illustrate that, for natural gas at a constant flow velocity of 20 m/s, a wall-thickness reduction of 0.37 mm per year is obtained. Even when the flow velocity is reduced to 10 m/s, or when a realistic velocity profile is used instead of a constant, maximum velocity, the model still predicts erosion rates that are far higher than what is observed in practice. In reality, erosion issues are not reported in the gas network, indicating that the assumed solid particle concentration significantly overestimates actual conditions.

Second, using the solid particle concentration from [11] in the natural-gas example of

Table 3-1 would imply extremely high particle mass flow rates in practice. For a flow velocity between 10 m/s and 20 m/s, the corresponding solid mass flow rate would be between 21 and 42 kg solids per day. This corresponds with 7.5 to 15 ton of solids per year, levels that are entirely

inconsistent with field experience. Routine maintenance on filtration systems does not reveal such high amounts. Filters are generally found to be still clean after annual maintenance checks. This is another indication that the solid particle concentration limits in [11] are not suitable for a realistic design procedure.

Large-scale, continuous field data on actual solid particle concentrations in the Dutch gas grid are unfortunately not available. The only found documented case that provided measurement data was the dust incident in the Wassenaar gas grid in December 2017 [12]. A series of domestic boiler malfunctions triggered an investigation, which concluded that historical dust was likely released due to maintenance work at a GOS station, causing a temporary reversal of flow direction. Measurements taken several days later showed solid concentrations of $< 0.001 \text{ mg/m}^3$ at multiple locations. At one flaring location—where high gas velocities occurred—a short term peak of 0.096 mg/m^3 was recorded, which dropped to $< 0.005 \text{ mg/m}^3$ within ten minutes and was still decreasing [12], [13]. These measurements indicate that, under normal operating conditions, the gas transport system is essentially dust-free, rendering erosion effects negligible. However, it also indicates that historically accumulated dust may be present and can be released over short time intervals under specific operational disturbances.

More realistic guidelines and standards for solid content are strongly recommended for hydrogen transport and distribution systems. The maximum solid particle concentration value defined in the *Ministeriële Regeling Gaskwaliteit* is not considered representative for actual operating conditions and leads to unrealistically high erosion predictions when applied to hydrogen transport.

Recent studies propose updated and more practically applicable limits for particle contamination in dedicated hydrogen infrastructure. For example, the report “*Study on hydrogen quality in dedicated infrastructure and standardisation*”, published by the EU Publications Office in 2025, provides input for the development of a harmonized European hydrogen quality standard [14]. This study recommends an indicative solid particle limit of 1 mg/kg for hydrogen transport systems. When expressed on a mass basis, this limit is more than a factor of 100 lower than the currently applied limit of $100 \text{ mg}/(\text{n})\text{m}^3$ for natural gas ($1 \text{ mg/kg} \approx 0.8 \text{ mg}/\text{nm}^3$), and more than a factor of 1000 lower when the normal density of hydrogen would be applied ($1 \text{ mg/kg} \approx 0.09 \text{ mg}/\text{nm}^3$).

The value of 1 mg/kg represents the permitted upper limit for continuous and steady entrainment of solid particles. In practice, however, the solid concentration in the gas network is not constant and may exhibit temporary increases. Significant incidental peaks above this limit could also occur, for example, following installation, commissioning or maintenance activities. The impact of such incidental increases depends on both the solid concentration and the duration of the exposure. As erosion is assumed to be linearly proportional to the solid concentration, the resulting effect can be relatively easily estimated provided that all other parameters remain unchanged. For instance, maintenance activities occurring once every ten years could result in a temporary increase in solid concentration from 1 mg/kg to 100 mg/kg for a duration of half a day. Due to the limited duration of this event, its contribution to the cumulative erosion is limited. When averaged over the full ten-year period, this scenario results in an increase of the total cumulative erosion of approximately 1.4% relative to the baseline scenario without maintenance. Even for this deliberately conservative scenario of maintenance every 10 years, the impact of such short term concentration peaks on long-term erosion remains limited. Nevertheless, while the erosion impact of such transient events is minor, maintaining solids concentrations as low as reasonably practicable at all times remains advisable.

Defining a new, universally applicable maximum solid particle concentration limit is not straightforward at this stage. However, it is clear that the currently used value of 100 mg/(n)m³ is unrealistic to apply as constant solid particle concentration. A significantly stricter limit on allowable solid content is necessary to avoid overly conservative constraints on maximum allowable hydrogen flow velocities.

3.5 Maximum flow velocities tables

Based on the assessment of more realistic flow profiles (section 3.3) and solid particle concentration (section 3.4), tables were developed to quantify their effect on the maximum allowable flow velocity. Transport and distribution system designers can use these tables to determine the maximum allowable flow velocity, to ensure acceptable erosion rates. For this assessment, a total allowable erosion wear of 1 mm over a design lifetime of 50 years was assumed, corresponding to a maximum average wall thickness loss of 0.02 mm per year. The results are presented, for erosion effects in elbows. Elbows considered as the most critical items in the pipe system (together with T-joints). For straight pipes, the erosion rates are significantly less critical and can be neglected if the erosion rates on the critical elements are demonstrated to be acceptable.

The total allowable wall-thickness loss is case-specific and depends on parameters such as the selected pipe schedule, operating pressure, corrosion allowance and other design considerations. To illustrate this sensitivity, the appendix also includes tables based on alternative allowable wall-thickness losses, thereby covering a representative bandwidth of design scenarios.

Maximum allowable flow velocities were calculated for three different operational flow scenarios:

1. Constant flow scenario
2. Flow profile based on the most conservative network case, with a mixture of industrial and householding usage.
3. Flow profile based on a network with industrial usage only

The predictions consider three different solid-content values: 1 mg/kg, 10 mg/kg, and 100 mg/kg of solid mass per mass of transported gas. For a line pressure of 8 barg erosion predictions are done for natural gas and hydrogen. For the line pressure of 16 barg only hydrogen is shown, since this is not an existing scenario for natural gas. Maximum allowable flow velocities refer to the highest instantaneous velocity that may occur during the lifetime.

Figure 3-5. Maximum allowable flow velocities corresponding to a wall thickness reduction of 0.02 mm/year for a DN200 steel elbow configuration (R=1.5D) operating at 8 bar line pressure. Flow velocities are highlighted in red when they fall below 20 m/s for natural gas (NG) or below 60 m/s for hydrogen (H₂).

Figure 3-6. Maximum allowable flow velocities corresponding to a wall thickness reduction of 0.02 mm/year for a DN200 steel elbow configuration (R=1.5D) operating at 16 bar line pressure. Flow velocities are highlighted in red when they fall below 60 m/s for hydrogen (H₂).

It is clearly observed that lower solid loadings and the use of a more realistic flow profile, instead of a constant-flow assumption, result in higher allowable maximum flow velocities. Although the allowable velocities for hydrogen are generally higher than those for natural gas, they do not always permit increasing the hydrogen flow to 60 m/s. It requires a combination of lower solid content and a more favorable flow profile. For 100 mg/kg solid content all the maximum allowable velocities remain below 60 m/s.

Increasing the operating pressure to 16 barg reduces the maximum allowable flow velocities compared with the 8 barg case. Under 16 barg conditions, the 60 m/s requirement is met for the industrial flow profile for only a solid content of 1 mg/kg. When applying the Industrial + Householding flow profile the allowable flow velocity is 60 m/s for the 10 mg/kg solid content.

Higher flow velocities may also be achieved by selecting a pipe schedule with increased wall thickness. While this results in higher material costs, the additional wall thickness provides a greater allowance for erosion, allowing a larger reduction in wall thickness to be tolerated over the design life. This modification could also only be applied to the critical locations in the systems such as elbows and tee-sections. The implications of permitting a wall thickness loss of 2 mm over a 50 year period are presented in the appendix. Consequently, higher flow velocities may be considered acceptable under such assumptions. However, this does not imply that a flow velocity of 60 m/s is universally acceptable for all operating scenarios.

In particular, as a realistic assessment of maximum allowable flow velocity in 16 barg networks, a typical value of 50 m/s is proposed, in case the solid particle concentration is limited to 1 mg/kg.

3.6 Re-use of as-built systems and future systems

Future hydrogen transport will include both the re-use of existing natural gas pipelines and the development of new dedicated hydrogen infrastructure. These two scenarios differ in terms of historical contamination, design philosophy, and erosion relevance.

3.6.1 Re-use of as-built pipeline systems

Historical experience and literature show that gas pipelines may contain residual solid particles. Although the occurrence of such contamination has decreased significantly compared to earlier decades (e.g. the era of town gas and early gas heating systems), due to improved materials, corrosion control, and gas treatment, solids may still be present. Under normal operating conditions, these particles could be deposited within the pipeline and not transported, as a minimum lift-off velocity is required for entrainment [14].

When existing pipelines are re-used for hydrogen service, flow velocities will increase compared to natural-gas operation. This may lead to temporary entrainment of historically deposited solids, resulting in a short term increase in solid particle transport. As discussed in Section 3.4, the erosion impact of such incidental solids release is expected to be limited, provided that the duration is short and flow velocities remain within the defined design limits.

However, if filtration between pipeline sections containing historical solids and downstream end use equipment (e.g. domestic boilers) is insufficient, solids contamination may lead to operational issues, as illustrated by the incidents in the Wassenaar gas grid in December 2017. While such events do not primarily represent an erosion risk, they constitute a relevant integrity and reliability concern. Where such risks cannot be fully mitigated, additional inspection and, if necessary, cleaning of pipeline sections prior to hydrogen operation should be considered

3.6.2 Newly developed hydrogen infrastructure

For newly developed hydrogen pipelines, recent design studies indicate that larger diameters are selected, resulting in maximum flow velocities well below the commonly referenced value of 60 m/s. In addition to benefits related to buffering capacity and reduced pressure drop, this approach also contributes to a reduced erosion risk. Consequently, reaching flow velocities up to 60 m/s may be less urgent for new infrastructure, whereas for re-using as-built pipelines erosion consideration may still impose limitations on the allowable flow velocities.

Finally, hydrogen produced via electrolysis or steam methane reforming is expected to be intrinsically very clean, with solid contamination only anticipated from external sources. Storage in salt caverns is also generally expected to result in clean hydrogen, whereas storage in former gas reservoirs requires adequate filtration. Maintaining solid contamination at a minimum throughout the complete gas network is essential to enable higher flow velocities and reliable operation. Therefore adequate filtration (design and periodic inspection) remains of key importance for hydrogen transport systems.

3.7 Conclusions

Realistic flow profiles combined with representative solid particle concentrations results in substantially higher allowable flow velocities than those derived under a constant flow assumption paired with very high (conservative) solids concentration. The constant worst-case assumptions are assumed to overestimate the erosion risk.

Table 3-2 presents the maximum flow velocities for hydrogen transport at 8 bar and 16 bar in a DN200 steel elbow configuration, assuming an allowable erosion rate corresponding to a wall thickness loss of 1 mm over a 50-year design life. The results indicate that flow velocities of 60 m/s can only be achieved at low solids concentrations. However, a combination of lower solid concentrations and a more favorable and realistic flow profiles may permit higher flow velocities. For both the 8 bar and 16 bar networks, careful consideration must therefore be given to the expected

level of solids concentration and the actual flow distribution, otherwise, erosion may impose a limiting constraint on the maximum allowable flow velocity.

Table 3-2. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.02 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for an elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	1	62.5	86.7	142.1
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	10	33.0	45.8	75.0
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	100	17.4	24.1	39.8
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	1	50.4	69.8	114.4
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	10	26.5	36.8	60.4
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	100	14.0	19.4	31.8

A constant solids concentration has been assumed in this assessment. If significantly lower or higher solids concentrations distribution occur over a large portion of the system lifetime, this will have a substantial impact on the maximum allowable flow velocity. Conversely, short term deviations in solids content have a limited effect on the cumulative erosion.

Additional tables covering other operating conditions, pipe diameters, and allowable erosion rates are provided in the appendix. The results are applicable to default R=1.5D elbows, which are also applicable to other configuration, in a conservative manner. Only for short radius R=1D elbows, the allowable maximum flow velocity will be slightly lower. It is recommended to use a 5% safety margin in such cases. For the low-pressure network operated at 0.1 bar, erosion has a limited impact on the maximum allowable flow velocities. In contrast, at higher operating pressures, erosion can become a limiting factor, with maximum allowable velocities remaining below 60 m/s. This emphasizes the importance of maintaining a clean hydrogen transport system through adequate filtration. Higher flow velocities may also be accommodated by allocating additional wall thickness allowance at critical locations such as elbows and tee sections.

Appendix – Maximum flow velocity tables for erosion risk. Different operation conditions

Table 3-3. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.02 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 0.1 barg – HDPE	100	1	130.6	180.8	288.5
Hydrogen, 0.1 barg – HDPE	100	10	72.4	100.2	159.9
Hydrogen, 0.1 barg – HDPE	100	100	40.1	55.5	88.6
Hydrogen, 0.1 barg – HDPE	200	1	156.0	216.0	344.6
Hydrogen, 0.1 barg – HDPE	200	10	86.4	119.7	190.9
Hydrogen, 0.1 barg – HDPE	200	100	47.9	66.3	105.8

Table 3-4. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.02 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 8 bar – HDPE	200	1	24.1	33.4	53.3
Hydrogen, 8 bar – HDPE	200	10	13.6	19.1	30.0
Hydrogen, 8 bar – HDPE	200	100	11.1	15.0	18.8
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200 (*)	1	62.5	86.7	142.1
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	10	33.0	45.8	75.0
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	100	17.4	24.1	39.8

(*) Diameter has no effect for the maximum allowable flow velocity for hydrogen transport at 8 barg for an elbow configuration.

Table 3-5. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.02 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 16 barg - steel	400(*)	1	50.4	69.8	114.4
Hydrogen, 16 barg - steel	400	10	26.6	36.8	60.4
Hydrogen, 16 barg - steel	400	100	14.0	19.4	31.8

(*) Diameter has no effect for the maximum allowable flow velocity for hydrogen transport at 16 barg for an steel elbow configuration.

Table 3-6. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.02 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 40 barg – steel	600(*)	1	40.2	55.8	91.4
Hydrogen, 40 barg – steel	600	10	21.2	29.4	48.2
Hydrogen, 40 barg – steel	600	100	11.2	15.5	25.4

(*) Diameter has no effect for the maximum allowable flow velocity for hydrogen transport at 40 barg for an steel elbow configuration.

Appendix – Maximum flow velocity tables for erosion risk. Different wall thickness losses

Table 3-7. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.01 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	1	51.6	71.6	117.2
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	10	27.2	37.7	61.9
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	100	14.4	20.2	33.1
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	1	41.5	57.6	94.4
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	10	21.9	30.4	49.8
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	100	11.6	16.0	26.3

Table 3-8. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.02 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	1	62.5	86.7	142.1
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	10	33.0	45.8	75.0
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	100	17.4	24.1	39.8
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	1	50.4	69.8	114.4
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	10	26.5	36.8	60.4
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	100	14.0	19.4	7.3

Table 3-9. Maximum flow velocities for three different flow profiles for a maximum allowable wall thickness loss of **0.04 mm per year** according to DNV guidelines [2] for a R=1.5D elbow configuration.

Case Info	DN	Solid [mg/kg]	Maximum flow velocity [m/s]		
			Constant	Industrial Only	Industrial+Householding
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	1	75.8	105.2	172.3
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	10	40.0	55.5	90.9
Hydrogen, 8 bar – steel	200	100	21.1	29.3	48.0
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	1	61.0	84.7	138.7
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	10	32.2	44.7	73.2
Hydrogen, 16 bar - steel	200	100	17.0	23.6	38.6

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